

Preparatory work for a pupils' self-report-instrument on positioning towards lessons' content-based requirements: Item collection for validation and construction of a questionnaire

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Items grouped per dimension	Theoretically assigned category
Participation in the classroom	
1. Often I am quiet and participate by writing something: Then it is not noticed if I have not understood everything.	defensive distancing
2. I am happy when task solutions can be guessed or copied from others, the blackboard, or elsewhere.	defensive distancing
3. I act interested even if the topics bore me.	offensive distancing
4. Also, I try to say something smart when I haven't fully understood something.	offensive distancing
5. The content in class is OK, and I usually try to go along with it.	non-resistant engagement
6. If I don't understand something, I simply ask the teacher.	non-resistant engagement
7. Sometimes it's good if the lessons are boring because then I can think a few more thoughts of my own about the topics.	reflected engagement
8. If the lesson gets too boring for me, I try asking an interesting question about the topic.	reflected engagement
Attitude towards the lessons' contents and social context	
9. Even if a topic interests me, I would rather keep quiet about it.	defensive distancing
10. If my classmates explain something to me, I listen away and wait to be told the solution to a task.	defensive distancing
11. If I haven't understood something, it annoys me when my classmates then try to explain it to me.	offensive distancing
12. The content of the lessons is always boring. The other pupils think so too.	offensive distancing
13. I always find the content of the lessons really exciting.	offensive distancing
14. I like to practise familiar skills as well as to learn some new things sometimes.	non-resistant engagement
15. I don't worry if I don't understand everything immediately.	non-resistant engagement
16. In class, you learn less for life than for school. But that's OK.	reflected engagement
17. Even without teachers and grades, I would engage with a lot of the content one usually learns in class.	reflected engagement

Note. The responses to these statements would be requested with a Likert scale, from '1 = strongly disagree' to '5 = strongly agree'.